

National and International Environmental Law and Justice

The Unresolved Issues

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Dr. R. Venkatasamy
EnviroSolutions Ltd
Mauritius

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The two terms '*Ecological justice*' and '*Environmental Justice*' may appear to be often conflicting, since both gives the impression that one and the same issue in environmental law and justice is the subject of debates. However, there is a need to differentiate between the human environment, which include built up areas, towns, cities, population centres, and the natural environment that includes biodiversity, ecosystems, and ecosystem goods and services. Some might think that '*environmental justice*' also implies solely '*justice for the natural environment*', that is for nature and ecosystems; however, that is not its common practical meaning in the political and social spheres, as it is more often rather considered as an offshoot of social justice, although it is still commonly used for the natural environment.

However, in this discussion, avoidance of confusion is a necessity. The dominant meaning of social justice is justice for humans. The OECD defines human '*society*' as '*the aggregate of people living together in a more or less ordered community.*' Other common definitions confirm that the overwhelmingly dominant meaning is that a '*society*' is a group or community of people, and social justice is about justice within human societies, and for human societies, or human individuals within the environment in which they live.

Social justice has also been applied to issues related to distribution of environmental '*goods*' such as resources, and '*bads*' such as pollution. This again has mostly been too often defined by the confusing term '*environmental justice.*' A further and more explicit definition of social justice has been proposed by Schlosberg (2007) as:

Equitable distribution of environmental risks and benefits; fair and meaningful participation in environmental decision-making; recognition of community ways of life, local knowledge, and cultural difference; and the capability of (human) communities and individuals to function and flourish in society.

However, Vucetich et al. (2018), basing their arguments on what other scholars have been discussing about '*just conservation*' and '*social justice*', have attempted to redefine social justice as the '*fair treatment of others,*' where the others are left open, and may also include nonhuman nature. Schlosberg (2007) similarly argues that while most definitions of the term are all primarily about justice for humans, social justice should necessarily include natural systems. So no doubt the term '*Ecojustice*' may be more fitting and less confusing when discussing the association of justice with the Rights of Nature or the Rights of Ecosystems.

To this day, the EPA's (USA) definition of Environmental Justice is what has been generally followed by other countries, and it states:

Environmental justice is the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin, or income with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies. ... It will be achieved when everyone enjoys the same degree of protection from environmental and health hazards and equal access to the decision-making process to have a healthy environment in which to live, learn, and work.

The EPA's definition can be considered as purely anthropocentric or human-centred since it places humans at the centre of the frame. Hence, environmental justice as commonly understood cannot properly be equated to ecological justice, as it expresses no concern for the nonhuman, *per se*, nor does it explicitly address the importance of protecting species, collectives, or ecological systems. Essentially, this type of justice is anthropocentric, as opposed to ecological justice, or Ecojustice, which is mainly ecocentric/biocentric, and the discussions of Cafaro et al. (2017), Washington et al. (2017) and Picolo et al. (2018) deal more explicitly with the intricacies of ecological justice, and its treatment within existing human-centred environmental agreements, laws, justice systems, and mindsets.

There are several definitions of Ecojustice, and probably the most appropriate would be a blend of the definitions proposed by Schlosberg ((2004) and Washington (2019):

Ecological justice is distinct from and more inclusive than environmental justice, and is concerned with other species independent of their instrumental value for humans.....given that it is proper to refer to human nature and nonhuman nature, there is similarly no ethical or philosophical problem with talking about '*ecological justice*' – justice for nonhumans. This acknowledges what we see as a great moral crime that society has carried out for the last few centuries ignoring that the nonhuman also deserves justice.

It makes sense then that discussing issues associated with environmental/ecological justice cannot ignore that for justice to prevail there must also be the notion of rights and wrongs; Environmental/Ecological rights have been discussed and summarized by Venkatasamy (2022). There are numerous definitions as to what the rights of nature (environmental/ecological) should be, but one from the Global Alliance for the Rights of Nature (GARN-2019) is the most fitting:

When we talk about the '*rights of nature*,' it means recognizing that ecosystems and natural communities are not merely property that can be owned, but are entities that have an independent right to exist and flourish. Laws recognizing the rights of nature thus change the status of natural communities and ecosystems to being recognized as rights-bearing entities with rights that can be enforced by people, governments, and communities.

The eternally contested view or mindset is whether humans are actually part of the planet's biodiversity and ecosystem, or as the common belief is, masters, owners, and shapers of ecological systems.

To keep the thread of the discussion flowing from one issue to another, it has been found best to discuss the greater picture of environmental justice first, then move to ecojustice.

Environmental Justice

Definitions of Environmental Justice comes in many forms, and appears to be solely human-centred as expressed in the globally accepted EPA's definition, in other words a one-way affair, as reflected in the comprehensive definition of Lewis (2012) that states:

Inequality or unfairness in the distribution of environmental burdens, where there is exclusion from the processes which determine how that distribution will be effected, or where disproportionate distribution is not balanced by sufficient reparation. This extends to potential injustices between developed and developing states, and between present and future generations.

Given such inequities, or injustices, the Club of Rome Report, '*Limits to Growth*,' (Meadows et al, 1972) thus advocates for some partial reduction in such an imbalance:

A deceleration of material growth in developed nations, in order to allow for it in the poorest nations.....a society based on justice and equality is much more likely to move towards a state of global balance than the expanding society we are currently experiencing.

The *Limits to Growth* is obviously more concerned about material growth through the disparate exploitation and consumption of natural resources, leading to socioeconomic rather than environmental ecological forms on injustices. Both The Club of Rome (1972) and Blanchon et al. (2009) introduce another dimension to environmental justice: '*Environmental Ethics*,' which has been extensively discussed by Nash (1989), Palmer et al. (2014), and Brennan and Lo. (2017). According to Blanchon (2009), it is both useful and important to distinguish three types of positioning in the relationship between humans and nature:

1. Perception of humans as separate from nature, either condemning our destructiveness or justifying our exploitiveness.
2. Although humans may exploit nature to resolve societal needs, both are eco-centered concepts of the environment and have little interest in the social dimension.
3. The third (more marginal) position looks beyond the human/nature dichotomy to build a broader ethics of the environment.

At the international level, the UN Conference on Environment and Development (RIO, 1992), gave rise to the concept of '*sustainable development*' (SD) based on environmental protection, in an attempt to give nature legitimacy. However, sustainable development emerged much earlier at the UN Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm in 1972, with the proposal of a new concept, '*Eco-Development*,' based on four principles:

1. The autonomy of decision-making and the pursuit of models specific to each ecological, historical, and cultural context;
2. Taking care of the needs of all humans equitably;
3. Ecological prudence; and
4. The pursuit of development that is in harmony with nature.

While the UN (1992) concept of sustainable development is regarded as prioritizing economic development over the natural environment, the flaws of the eco-development concept of 1972 has been analyzed and discussed by Sachs (1980), Harvey (1996), Fraser (2001) and Berr (2015), with a final consensus that the concept:

....is ecological devastation that penalizes some social groups more than others and represents a threat to future generations.

In addition to the prescriptions of the Club of Rome, the United Nations moved a step further and two decades later produced the '*Draft Principles on Human Rights and the Environment*' (1994), further proclaiming that:

All persons have the right to a secure, healthy, and ecologically sound environment. This right and other human rights, including civil, cultural, economic, political, and social rights, are universal, interdependent, and indivisible.

The United Nations '*Principles*' place humans above the environment and ecosystems, with rights of what that environment/ecosystem could or should produce and provide for their health and security, but failing to establish how that environment/ecosystem should be managed to sustain provision and production of these services to humans. It is interesting to note the mention of '*ecologically sound environment*' in the UN's Principles, inferring that there must somehow be some other frameworks that explain and ensure how that state could be achieved, maintained, and protected. If the concept of human environmental rights does not also imply that the environment that we live in and depend on should not also have rights that humans should respect, and that there are no instruments to ensure justice for that environment in case of harms, the concept is left with some missing links (Venkatasamy, 2021), and environmental ethics appear to have fallen by the wayside..

It appears most discussions at policymaking levels tend to place economic and human material development at the forefront, sidelining the importance of the health of both the natural and man-made environments. Sagoff (1995) claims that a typical argument belonging to such a position states:

The standard model of economic growth assumes that human knowledge and ingenuity can always alleviate resource shortages so that natural capital sets no limit on economic growth, and,...if there is a limiting factor in economic production, it is knowledge, and that as long as knowledge advances, the economy can expand.

While Sagoff (1995) emphasizes on the superiority of humans, the author obviously omits to take either the Club of Rome's '*Limit to Growth*' or the '*Planetary Boundaries*' concept of the Stockholm Resilience Centre (now Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research) seriously. The established connotation of the superiority of humans could never predict the outcomes of continued resource extraction that is leading to the situation of resource overdraft, with a probability of resource deficiency and exhaustion if the present pace of production and consumption through uncontrolled environmental destruction is maintained.

However, a year later Bookchin (1996) tries to bring reality into human actions and behaviour by declaring:

One of the most entrenched ideas in Western thought is the notion that nature is a harsh realm of necessity, a domain of unrelenting lawfulness and compulsion. From this underlying idea, two extreme attitudes have emerged. Either humanity must yield with religious or '*ecological*' humility to the dicta of '*natural law*' and take its abject place side by side with the lowly ants...or it must '*conquer*' nature by means of its technological and rational astuteness, in a shared project ultimately to '*liberate*' all of humanity from the compulsion of natural '*necessity*' - an enterprise that may well entail the subjugation of human by human.

Bookchin however never realized that the age of '*the subjugation of human by human*' would eventually become a reality, simply because humanity failed to liberate itself from '*the compulsion of natural necessity.*' Discouraging on the philosophical aspects of uncontrolled environmental destruction and the necessity for environmental justice is always necessary, but the practical realities and necessities are as important. In that sense, Taylor (1986) reminds that since the

beginning of modern ‘*conservationism*,’ environmental thinkers and nature advocates keep applying arguments about injustice related to environmental rights when making claims about human-environment relations, and therefore keep advocating for more and more environmental policies and action.

Taylor finds that, as a result, the birth of the environmental justice movement became the latest in a series of environmental mobilizations that employ the notion of injustice, but unlike its predecessors, the environmental justice movement makes the injustice framework explicit. In other words, concludes Taylor:

Environmental justice should not only acknowledge the existence of environmental injustice in the form of humans harming nature, it should also recognize that environmental injustice arises from racial, gender, and class discrimination.

While the UN keeps re-inventing sustainable development at the international level, Veyret and Simon (2006) discusses how sustainable development grew out of ‘*conservationism*,’ and the looming threats of a global environmental crisis in terms of pollution, deforestation, desertification, and global warming. Analyzing some of the ideas found in the concept of sustainable development in relation to environmental conservation and environmental justice, Veyret recognizes that two sources of inequity between the North and South stand out clearly:

1. Overconsumption of resources by nations in the North, appropriation of the atmosphere, the world’s oceans, and biodiversity by these same wealthy nations.
2. Exposure of the populations in the South to risks caused by lifestyles in the North that are of no benefit whatsoever to them at the local level.

Even if Veyret omits to mention land grabbing and the environmental/ecological destruction it entails in the South to satisfy the human needs of the North, these two issues give rise to the concept of ‘*ecological debt*,’ defined by Accion Ecologica (1999) as:

The debt accumulated by Northern industrial countries towards third world countries on account of resource plundering and use of environmental space to deposit wastes, modelled on the debt owed by developing nations to nations in the North.

At the international level, the issue of environmental equity between North and South remains unresolved, despite the possibility of differential treatment, technology transfer, or financial compensation. As Okereke (2008) emphasizes, while the principle of common but differentiated responsibility ‘*expresses intuitive notions of global justice*,’ taking past inequalities into account, ‘*its application has not generated any actual transfer of wealth or technology from North to South*.’ Okereke concludes that:

The concept of global environmental justice has experienced very limited success as a strategic resource for developing nations in their counter-hegemonic project to ensure comprehensive intra-generational equity.

Yet it is surely by digging into the concept of a nature-society hybrid that environmental issues including quality of life, access to resources, and equal distribution of both advantages and disadvantages derived from environmental conditions can best be viewed as social justice issues, and examined in the light of contemporary theories of justice.

Given such persisting situations, Schlosberg (2007) lists a number of points that should be included in global environmental justice:

- Equitable distribution of environmental risks and benefits;
- Fair and meaningful participation in environmental decision-making;

- Recognition of community ways of life, local knowledge, and cultural difference; and
- The capability of (human) communities and individuals to function and flourish in society.

Apart from Schlosberg (2007), who argues that environmental justice should include natural systems, most discussions are mainly about justice for humans. Hence, environmental justice cannot properly be equated to ecological justice, as it expresses no concern for the nonhuman *per se*, nor does it explicitly address the importance of protecting species, collectives, or environmental systems.

While the belief that environmental rights should be part and parcel of human rights still persists in international discussions, in their discourse about environmental rights and justice both Gibson (1990) and Macdonald (2008) argue that, while a rights-based approach to environmental protection and justice could be useful, the use of human right to a healthy environment may be problematic, in that it takes away a concept that should be more ecocentric from the general approach. It is the ecocentric inclusion within such rights that infer the natural environment we live in should also has rights, and that there should be judicial frameworks to ensure that such rights are observed and respected, claim the authors. The authors infer that there should be frameworks to ensure procedural environmental justice, and access to environmental justice.

It has also been proposed by Beretta (2012) that speaking of environmental justice or injustice in terms of legal redressment and compensation has the disadvantage of politicizing the environment. However, ecologists present it as a neutral field or as a high-minded cause that must gain full consensus. Beretta (2012) recognises that in what concerns the procedural aspects of justice,

The issue of enforcement is particularly telling because it is insufficient to have strong regulations against environmental injustice if discretion in their application effectively results in inaction or further injustice.

Another element that has been brought into discussions is that conflicts of interest may also impede procedural environmental justice, especially in those cases in which judgment is biased by financial, personal, or other obligations, explains Johnson and Rogers (2012). For instance, politicians may have conflicts of interest due to campaign donations on the part of developers, who expect favourable outcomes on environmental impact decisions. In addition, as Johnson and Rogers (2012) aptly puts it:

Access to justice frequently comes at a financial cost that is too great for the poor to pay.

Thus, in attempting to resolve issues associated with enforcement of environmental justice through the principle of compensation for environmental prejudice, and the resulting commodification of the environment poses a set of problems that are primarily ethical. It has been recognized well before that the system of commodifying environmental risks also helps maintain environmental injustices (Summers, 1991; Korten and Cobb, 1991), and the situation has rather worsened than improve today.

Discussing the difficulties in supporting approaches to resolve environmental injustices, South and Brisman (2013) explain how it is even more difficult to harmonise the effects of harms caused to both people and the environment, especially where both human and environmental rights are violated and destroyed. Earlier, Hulme (2009) established that environmental justice in any form requires action, but the major problem remains human self-

interest, and continually contesting evidence of harms prevents most from seeking genuine change while political will is swayed by short-term priorities, a situation that persists globally. Discussing the situation in the UK, as an example, Pedersen (2014) remarks that:

One thing which the British understanding of environmental justice shares with those developed elsewhere is a susceptibility to political neglect in accordance with executive winds of change.....environmental justice is today most notable by its absence when it comes to official directives, guidelines and statements.

The persisting existence and probably intentional perpetuation too, of such human induced problems keep pushing the realities of environmental justice away from human priorities. Discussing the intricacies of environmental justice, Gianolla, (2013) finds that environmental justice and human rights can be seen as tied together and there is some expression of this in various international treaties, national laws, and constitutions, and also in propositions that if there is to be justice, environmental rights should be seen as human rights. That is especially '*in cases where human rights regimes explicitly incorporate environmental rights for current and future generations.*' The argument presupposes that environmental justice therefore touches not only on human rights, but also treats social, economic, political, and cultural rights as being part and parcel of the same framework, ostentiously leaving '*ecological rights*' and '*ecological justice*' on the periphery. A situation that cannot lead to solutions.

All arguments and cross-talks about environmental justice raise important questions about how satisfactory current systems of applying or imposing regulation and law are in a world not only increasingly aware of, and increasingly facing changing environmental problems, but also increasingly controlled by vested interests. South (2014) claims that although awareness of environmental issues has expanded, the problem of response faces increasing tensions and dilemmas, concluding that:

Meanwhile, the political agenda has a tendency to move uncomfortable and difficult challenges up and down the scales of importance and urgency, with resources diminishing as the priority reduces.

In response to the many problems exposed by scholars, The UNDP, in its discourse on '*Environmental Justice: Comparative Experiences in Legal Empowerment*' (2014), states that the concept of environmental justice should concentrate on the inclusiveness of:

A mechanism of accountability for the protection of rights and the prevention and punishment of wrongs related to the disproportionate impacts of growth on the poor and vulnerable in society from rising pollution and degradation of ecosystem services, and from inequitable access to and benefits from the use of natural assets and extractive resources.

The UNDP re-invents the '*Limits to growth*' to a certain extent, producing yet another human-centred proposition that stresses on human needs, but not on the needs of nature on which humanity depends, and also not considering the wrongs that humans do to nature. It is correct to say that the poor and vulnerable suffer more from environmental degradation and mismanagement, but that does not mean the rich are not affected too. Diversions have never been a solution to environmental management. The enacting of appropriate environmental laws and frameworks for the application of justice to and for the environment would be the solution. It should also not be a matter of engaging in committed geographical work that seeks not only to define and describe socio-environmental inequalities and forms of environmental segregation, but also a responsibility of seeking and highlighting the processes upstream that produce these inequalities, as has been proposed and discussed by Okereke (2008; 2010).

What is interesting to note is that even if humanity depends strongly on nature to flourish and survive, humans keep asking for protective measures against the harms they themselves cause to the natural environment, atmospheric pollution and global warming being the most recent. The understanding that less harm caused to nature would mean a better environment for all living beings does not appear to arise. Essentially, environmental justice to this day turns out to be purely anthropocentric, and the implications have been discussed variously (Cafaro et al., 2017; Piccolo et al., 2018). However, right now humanity appears to be stuck with anthropocentrism, and contented with it.

In 2019, Ramirez-Andreotta suggested a list of 17 guidelines with regards to environmental justice, and 2 points are worth quoting:

- Environmental justice should affirm the sacredness of Mother Earth, ecological unity and the interdependence of all species, and the right to be free from ecological destruction.
- Environmental justice requires that we, as individuals, make personal and consumer choices to consume less and reprioritize our lifestyles to ensure the health of the natural world for present and future generations

Ramirez-Andreotta (2019) tries to reverse the present situation from one that is human-centred (anthropocentric) to one that should be bio-centric or eco-centred (ecocentric). That is a philosophy that may work at national levels, but not really on the international arena. Four South American countries, Columbia, Bolivia, Chile and Panama appear to be going in the right direction, the one proposed by Ramirez-Andreotta, that is adopting a '*nature first*' philosophy. According to Oliver et al. (2015) it is also self-defeating if long-term human flourishing remains the main objective, as society depends fully on nature to flourish and survive, a nature that needs to be nurtured and protected.

Ecological Justice-Ecojustice

Before even attempting to define ecological justice there need to be a clear understanding of what ecology and ecosystems are about. Bronfenbrenner (1994) and Balee (2014) are in agreement on one definition of ecology:

Ecology is a branch of biology that focuses on the interrelationship of organisms and their environment.

The Oslo Manifesto for Ecological Law and Governance (2016) defines an ecosystem as:

A community or group of living organisms that live and interact with each other in a specific environment.

To establish the difference between environmental and ecological justice, Dobson (1998) suggests that:

One way to describe the distinction between the two is that environmental justice presents the environment as an ingredient of justice whereas ecological justice regards the environment (or certain parts of it) as a recipient of justice

According to the theories and discussions of Miller (1991), the differences are clear-cut and distinguishable, since:

Environmental justice concerns the management of environmental matters within human communities. These matters include, for example, nature-related benefits and burdens of human activities, environmental quality, and environmental decision-making. Ecological justice, in contrast, is about justice between humans and the nonhuman world: it expands the community of justice beyond human beings.

In addition, Miller perceives ecological justice as:

Ecological justice discourse concerns justice in human-nonhuman relations and views at least some nonhuman entities as recipients of justice. This is a more radical stance compared to those views that reserve the community of justice for humans and argue ‘*merely*’ for transforming the contents but not recipients of justice.

Pascual et al. (2017) find that even before attempting to discuss ecological justice, defining nature, which remains a fundamental problem in the first instance, becomes of necessity to effectively establish a case for the rights of nature, as a prerequisite for legal instruments to ensure justice for ecosystems (ecojustice). Perhaps the most comprehensive definition of nature is from the Lexico Dictionary:

The phenomena of the physical world collectively, including plants, animals, the landscape, and other features and products of the earth, as opposed to humans or human creations.

For a proper definition of Ecological Justice, one may combine the thoughts of Schlosberg, (2004), Baxter, (2005), Shoreman-Ouimet and Kopnina, (2015) and Washington (2019):

Ecological justice is distinct from and more inclusive than environmental justice, and is concerned with other species independent of their instrumental value for humans. It is associated with ‘*biospheric altruism*’, and extends beyond human beings. Given that it is proper to refer to human nature and nonhuman nature, there is similarly no ethical or philosophical problem with talking about ‘*ecological justice*’—justice for nonhumans. This acknowledges what we see as a great moral crime that society has carried out for the last few centuries ignoring that the nonhuman also deserves justice.

In his discourse on Eco-Justice, Alrøe (2005) reflects that while environmental justice is most commonly used, eco-justice more aptly describes the relationship between the systemic problems facing individuals, communities and the natural world, which is made up of a variety of relationships, including people, creatures, eco-systems, economy, environment, food, water, air, and rules facilitating social, cultural, spiritual and emotional well-being of all ‘*in a home which is held in common.*’

Analyzing the ever-present dominance of humans over nature, Curry (2011) observes that, with regards to justice, wherever there are conflicts between humans and nature, humans continue to take precedence, rightfully or wrongfully. This, explains Curry, is simply because humans, the lawmakers, have laws to protect them and can seek justice while nature does not have such privileges. With regard to justice for nature, existing frameworks and processes have been operating under the umbrella of ‘*social justice,*’ and have mostly been defined by the confusing term ‘*environmental justice.*’ Some might think that environmental justice is actually ‘*justice for the environment*’, that is for nature; however, Curry expounds on how within the common present academic meaning, it is a mere offshoot of social justice.

It is now established and accepted that ecological justice should be regarded as being distinct from and more inclusive than environmental justice, and excludes the theory of ‘*justice of the distribution of environmental goods among people,*’ often mentioned, and has been extensively discussed by Low and Gleeson (1998). Additionally, there is a realization of another relational aspect to the struggle for ecological justice: that of our relationship as a species of human beings to the rest of the natural world. Low and Gleeson (1998) term the first as ‘*environmental justice*’ and the latter as ‘*ecological justice,*’ but point out that ‘*they are really two aspects of the same relationship.*’

Before even discussing justice for ecosystems, or ecojustice, the very first step should be in establishing rights for nature and ecosystems, analyzed and discussed by Venkatasamy (2022), and establishing the case for justice from a background of injustice. There can only be a call for justice when injustice can be shown. While it is generally assumed that justice and injustice are only applicable to relations among creatures considered '*moral equals*', in other words humans, Barry (1999) contends that the ethical and moral issues associated with the human treatment of nature should not be simply considered as acts representing right and wrong, but of justice or injustice for which there should be instruments of punishment or redressment. Dobson (1998) adds that leaving nature and animals out of traditional theories of justice is much more of a strategy concocted '*out of a desire to exclude nature, and not from sound theoretical reasoning.*' The reasons, claims Dobson, centres around the fear of giving nature an equal moral footing with humans.

Both Dobson (1998) and Barry (1999) clearly demonstrate how for decades anthropocentrism has refused to consider that nonhuman nature also has a right to justice, a denial that according to Dobson represents:

A major obstacle to reaching a viable concept of justice that encompasses both humans and nature, and hence achieving a holistic conservation strategy for planet Earth.

The analysis of Low Gleeson (1998), supported by the discussion of Ehresman and Stevis (2018) establishes and recognises that ecological justice, apart from being about fairness to others with regard to the environment, goes beyond environmental/ecological justice, that is the recognition that minority and low-income communities often bear a disproportionate share of environmental costs. The perception that this is unjust has also been discussed by Massey (2004), and Schroeder et al. (2008), and the authors relate how environmental justice researchers have focused on either the intragenerational issues of environmental justice, or the intergenerational dimensions of environmental justice as connected to sustainability, though the two are interconnected discourses on environmental justice and ecological sustainability, and have been explicitly analyzed and discussed by Goodland (1995) and Glotzbach and Baumgärtner (2012).

Originating from the concepts of environmental ethics, arguments and calls for justice to nonhumans, or calls for ecological justice appeared during the 1970s and 1980s, with arguments from such eminent scholars as Holmes Rolston III (1985; 1993; 2001), Taylor (1986), and Arne Naess (1989). Early discussions were however vague regarding the relation between the realm of justice and that of ethics and moral concern.

However, the concept of ecological justice, apart from having been ignored for too long by environmental scholars in their approach to justice, has always had to face opposition that has also been strong, and mostly unjustified. The reasoning of Rawls (1971) contends that a clear distinction exists between the sphere of moral concern and the field of justice, arguing that:

We can only have moral duties of compassion for humanity, but not duties of justice to sentient animals.

Rawls appear to be mainly concerned about '*sentient*' animals, recognising on the one hand that sentience can be attributed to animals, but ignoring the complexity of ecosystems on the other. Similarly, Brian Barry (1997; 1999) claims that '*justice cannot be applied outside human relations,*' an attitude that many would call anthropocentric, that is purely human-centred, and unjustified by any ethical or moral norms.

However, Bell (2006) finds that Rawls' theory of justice as fairness and concern only for human beings excluding nonhumans from justice considerations lacks insightfulness. Widely discussed (Eckersley 1996, 1999, 2004, 2020; Schlosberg, 2007, 2012, 2019a), ecological justice adopts an expansive view, and calls for the advocates of ecological justice to note that:

The idea of sentience should not be a necessary condition for an entity to become a victim of injustice.

Defining alternative criteria for identifying those entities that can encounter injustices is a central theme of ecological justice literature. Potential candidates for such criteria involve having interests, being able to flourish, or being a living being or process with capabilities and integrity.

Given a certain lack of understanding and appreciation of the value of ecosystems to the community of humans, as early as 1973 Naess acknowledged that humanity was ignoring a great moral crime that society has been committing for the last few centuries, ignoring that the nonhuman also deserves justice. Naess was specifically referring to humans ignoring the necessity for ecological justice as justice between the human and non-human species, or the necessity to protect non-human species from the exploitative culture of humans. In other words, a necessity to recognise the importance of legal frameworks and justice for ecosystems, or ecojustice as it is defined. Almost three decades later, Low and Gleeson (1998) re-affirmed the theories of Naess regarding the relationship between people and the rest of the natural world, defining ecojustice by its simplest definitive terms: '*justice for nonhuman nature.*'

Nevertheless, the debate around justifying nature's rights, justice for nature and ecojustice specifically has been ongoing for decades with both opposing and sympathetic views and propositions. The first kind of objection arises mainly from the political philosophy that the ability to participate in contract formulation and voluntary cooperation is what makes humans capable of belonging in the community of justice. The same reason, then, excludes any non-rational entities from that community. This assumption that reciprocity of justice requires moral agency is characteristic of objections to ecological justice as argued by Baxter (2005). Nicholas Low and Brendan Gleeson (1998) propose the community of justice should include all natural entities, both individuals and collectives, because '*every natural entity is entitled to enjoy the fullness of its own form of life.*' In conflict cases, further principles of precedence could and should be applied, propose Low and Gleeson (1998).

The opposition is also reflected in a discussion on the morality of freedom (Raz, 1986), who argues that a person or other entity has a right '*if and only if they are capable of having rights,*' and that some aspect of their interest or well-being would be '*a sufficient reason for holding some other person(s) to be under a duty.*' Raz (1986) further argues that the theory of interest itself, associated with nature/ecosystems as has been proposed, does not resolve:

Whether nature is capable of having rights, suggesting that entities that have value for their own sake, rather than for the value they provide others, can have rights.

Those who dispute that ecosystems/nature should have rights always support their arguments on the superiority of humans. Van De Veer and Pierce (1986) emphasize on that perception by declaring:

Persons are rational, autonomous beings, capable of formulating and pursuing different conceptions of good; persons have ends of their own but things or objects do not and persons may never be treated as means to an end, however worthy that end.

Persons (humans) have rights because of their unconditional worth as rational beings, and whereas the worth of things is relative to the ends of persons, claim the authors. However, the authors do accept human duties to what they refer to as '*inanimate objects*,' even accepting Kant's 1997 observations that:

A propensity to exploit or destroy nonhuman and inanimate nature might violate a person's duty to himself.

However, a number of scholars support the concept of justice for ecosystems or ecojustice, including Low and Gleeson (1998), Baxter (2005) Schlosberg (2007; 2014), and reject the opposing mainstream stance of critics from the liberal justice spheres as inadequate and argue for expanding the community of justice to include the human-nature relationship, or at least some forms of them, into the realm of justice. Most supporters of ecojustice insist that the discourse of ecological justice does not necessitate expanding the realm of social justice based on arguments that '*social justice does not define the whole community of justice*.' Both Bowers (2001) and Baxter (2005) remark that in spite of academic discussions on ecocentrism so far, little has been shown in terms of ecological justice globally. The authors lament that discussions about ecojustice have largely been ignored so far, and have not been '*foregrounded in regard to conservation*.' Bowers and Baxter further find that whenever the question of '*justice*' for nature arises, approaches to the concept are strongly influenced by anthropocentric bias.

However, and contrary to the beliefs of Bowers (2001) and Baxter (2005), Boyd (2017) believes that whether nature should be endowed with moral rights is likely to remain debated, but nature clearly can have legal rights, as has been shown in jurisdictions that have recognized, granted, or enacted them. There have been many discussions about the subject, and those of Feinberg (1980), Nussbaum (2006), Stone (2010), and Mace et al.(2018) all add up to valid information and arguments. These two opposing scenarios set the scene for a further discussion about whether nature has rights, and whether ecojustice should now be part of judicial instruments, nationally and internationally.

The likely reason as to why acceptance of ecological rights and justice for ecosystems have been opposed, probably due to a lack of understanding of the functions of ecosystems, may also be attributed to the inability of some scholars to understand how nature/ecosystems participate in human development, and where ecojustice should fit. Analyzing the discussion of Miller (1991) on the concept of ecojustice, at least three different common issues appear to persist:

1. The general set of attitudes about justice and the environment at the center of which is dissatisfaction with traditional theories of justice.
2. The anthropocentric and egocentric Western moral and ethical systems that have remained unconcerned with species, oceans, wilderness areas, and other parts of the biosphere, except as they may be used by humans.
3. Anything which is non-human is viewed mainly as raw material for human uses, largely or completely without moral standing.

And in a discussion on '*The challenge of ecological justice in a globalising world*,' Hugo Alrøe (2005) pushes the likely fields of ecojustice further, and establishes that ecological justice should be applied to three related aspects of the present trends:

1. The commodification of hitherto commons,
2. The externalisation of environmental and social costs, and
3. Globalisation as the erosion of barriers to distant trade and ownership.

Miller (1991) finds that, relying mainly upon holistic principles of biocentrism and deep ecology, environmentalists suggest that the '*ecojustice*' alternative that considers the value of non-human life forms should be independent of the '*usefulness of the non-human world for human purposes.*' As such, Miller insists that the central idea of ecojustice should consider expanding the categories of ethical and moral considerations relevant to justice to encompass nature itself and its constituent parts. The author contends that human beings have an obligation to take the inherent value of other living things into consideration whenever these living things are affected by human actions. The elements of such a philosophical approach to environmental and ecological justice have been discussed and elaborated upon in the works of Schlosberg (2007; 2019a; b).

Miller (1991) further contends that the elements comprising the broad framework of environmental and ecological justice must provide fresh and useful insights into such topics as species extinctions and ecosystem wellbeing, proposing that:

1. Ecological justice should insist on expanding the community of justice to nonhuman individuals, both sentient and non-sentient ones, and ecological systems broadly.
2. Broadness of the framework should also involve broadening the contents of justice.
3. The approach should reject the view that justice is primarily about distribution and endorse instead the relational view of justice as a matter of relations between recipients of justice, where distribution plays a role but is not the whole of justice.

In other words, the ecological approach to justice should involve a transition from a distributional to a relational or rational paradigm of justice. Similar to the reasoning concerning inclusivity and relationships of Alroe, Miller (1991) concludes his discussion by elaborating as to why there should be a necessity to redirect the concept of ecojustice away from concentrating specifically on equal rights for humans and nonhumans, to include such other issues as climate change, where the distribution of atmosphere-related goods and bads have become primary issues, and other '*new*' issues such as the preservation of cultures and places, the impacts of climate change on the rest of the natural world (not just on humans), species extinctions and the multitude of ethical challenges related to global environmental harm in general.

Species extinctions resulting from anthropocentric human activities have also been discussed as yet another instance of injustice to ecosystems that may have serious repercussions on human wellbeing, calling for renewed efforts to make ecojustice a reality, for both nature and humans. The findings of Purvis et al. (2000) regarding the extent of extinctions presently, as mentioned by Miller (1991), and after analyzing the possible worsening of the situation if all aspect of sustainability and ecological preservation and justice are not taken seriously and immediately, result in Purvis et al. concluding that:

Current and projected species extinction rates exceed geologically normal background rates by several orders of magnitude, indicating that we face an extinction episode equivalent to mass extinctions of the paleontological past.

Buckley (2016) and Vucetich et al., (2017) are similarly concerned about extinctions discussed by Miller (1991) and Purvis et al. (2000) and associate the lack of justice for both the environment in general and ecosystems in particular as being part of the cause, stating that:

Despite the development of a large body of social and ecological literature, we are today further than ever from addressing and stopping this mass extinction.

The fear of these ‘*projected species extinction rates*’ as a result of injustice appears to be more of a reality today, with the numerous reports confirming extinction of species at an alarming rate, an event that has been associated with human anthropocentric activities and lifestyles. In spite of past and current debates about whether this mass extinction actually needs to be averted, there are some propositions that it can be accommodated by letting supposedly non-essential species go extinct, that is if humanity is ever able to select these ‘*non-essential specie,*’ however preposterous ignoring the complexity of natural systems would be. Even if Nicole Hassoun (2011) proposes that ‘*problems for many parts of nature will probably be good for some other parts,*’ there is an urgent necessity to develop an ecocentric worldview to accept that human and nonhuman organisms, species, ecosystems, and ecosystem processes are all inter-connected and entitled to moral value; ecocentric value systems dictates that all natural entities have both ‘*intrinsic*’ or ‘*inherent*’ values as proposed by Curry, (2011), Callicott, (2017) and Washington et al., (2017).

Contrary to the influence and effects of endless academic discussions about whether nature should or should not have rights, growing global consciousness of environmentalism in tandem with increasing threats to social and environmental sustainability, and the recent issue of climate change, have contributed to the greening of constitutions in several countries. The frequent high-profile global summits on environmental matters in Stockholm (1972), Rio (1992), Kyoto (1997), Rio again (2012), and Paris (2015), among dozens of others, seem to have influenced drafters of domestic constitutions, who have included sustainable development, climate change, biodiversity protection, and other environmental matters within their constitutional texts. However, what has been missing all through is serious thinking about nature’s rights, and the urgency for ecological laws as a global urgency.

The difficulties in achieving a global consensus on ecological rights and ecojustice have no doubt been mainly because of established anthropocentric and human-centered mindsets, and unwillingness to flexibility through fears of uncertainties towards relatively more ecocentric/biocentric philosophies, especially in the capital-oriented systems of the industrialized North. The stagnation of discussions to that end remains due to the inability to understand the true relationship between humans and nature, and Rowe (1994) tries to alleviate fears in a conciliatory statement:

Ecocentrism is not an argument that all organisms have equivalent value. It is not an anti-human argument, nor a put-down of those seeking social justice. It does not deny that myriad important homocentric problems exist. Nevertheless, it stands aside from these smaller, short-term issues in order to consider Ecological Reality. Reflecting on the ecological status of all organisms, it comprehends the Ecosphere as a Being that transcends in importance any one single species, even the self-named sapient one.

Picking up on the concept of ‘*ecological status of all organisms*’ of Rowe (1994) and in asking the question ‘*Whose Ecological Justice?*’ Stevis (2000) contends that subscribing to either ecocentric or ecological justice visions of nature could be both liberating and dangerous.

1. Liberating because:

- They disrupt the imperial parameters of anthropocentrism.
- They deliver us from scientific and naturalistic views of nature.

2. Dangerous because:

- They can suggest that we are all equally implicated in harming nature.
- They can suggest that nature is nothing but another distribution issue.

Stavis finds that an increased prominence in environmental justice movements emphasizing on distribution has necessitated a distinction between environmental and ecological justice. As a consequence, and according to the theories of Low and Gleeson (1998), the struggle for ecojustice as shaped by the politics of the environment has given rise to two relational aspects:

1. The justice of the distribution of environmental goods and harms among people, and
2. The justice of the relationship between humans and the rest of the natural world.

Discussing ecojustice from the distributive angle, Schlosberg, (2001; 2004) argues that social and environmental justice are commonly based on the idea of distributive justice, looking at how ‘*goods*’ such as resources, or ‘*bads*’ such as pollution are distributed amongst society. However, Schlosberg (2001) is of the opinion that the idea of distributive justice can also be applied to nature, noting that ecological justice demands an ‘*extension of recognition*’ to nature. It requires that nature be seen as ‘*another*’ that merits justice, especially when it is on the distributive end of the ‘*bads*,’ explains Schlosberg. Additionally, Baxter (2005) argues that nonhuman species have a moral right to distributive justice, which entails:

Recognizing their claim to a fair share of the environmental resources which all life-forms need to survive and to flourish.

According to Baxter, the interconnectedness of humans and natural systems necessarily needs recognition and protection, if the continuation of life on the planet were to be guaranteed, stating that:

Ecological justice promotes fairness in relation to the common environment for both present and future generations and for both human and other living beings, being therefore a more comprehensive form of justice than the well-known form from political liberalism, extended to incorporate the idea that individuals have a claim on their environment and the idea that justice and fairness concern not only humans, but animals and other living organisms as well.

The concept of distributive justice in relation to nature’s/ecosystems’ rights of legal protection has been extensively discussed by Sievers-Glotzbach (2013). In the attempt to broaden and deepen environmental justice, Stevis (2000) finds that a promising and necessary, but not necessarily sufficient strategy for such an outcome is a political economy that prohibits the displacement of environmental harm across space or time, as discussed by Wapner (1997), Benton (1996) and Harvey (1996) in the sense that:

Since ecological justice cannot be considered a default outcome of socialist politics (and the same applies to the emancipation of gender, sexual preferences and so on) ecological politics is a necessary ingredient of socialist politics.

In conclusion, Stevis (2000) claims that:

Investing non-human nature with differential values, rights, and hierarchies may facilitate our ethical decisions but it is intrusive and, most likely, unnecessary.

Associating human development with future generations, the analysis and discussion Sudhir and Sen (2000) attempt at integrating the concern for human development in the present with that in the future (future generations), but find that in arguing for sustainable human development, it appeals to the notion of ethical ‘*universalism*,’ which stands for an elementary demand for impartiality of claims applied within and between generations. Economic sustainability is often seen as a matter of intergenerational equity, but the specification of what is to be sustained is not always straightforward, observe the authors. Sustainable economic development is known to be human-centric and exclude the welfare of nature and ecosystems, the providers of human needs.

The work of Sen (2001) concentrates on the notion that sustainability should be about ‘*conserving a capacity to produce well-being*’ for people in the future, as opposed to the purely economic development proposed by economists. Sen proposes that future generations of humans should have the freedom to enjoy the same environmental benefits that earlier generations enjoyed. However, how far to go back in time to establish the standard remains problematic. The world can only offer the present state of the environment to future generations, whether it is acceptable or not. Sen (2001) concludes that:

Any system that would limit the freedoms and capabilities of future generations, and limits the environmental possibilities for those generations, would be unjust.

Bringing the notion of capabilities in to discussion, and supporting the reflections of Sen (2001), Breena Holland (2008) argues for an ‘*instrumental consideration of the environment in the capabilities approach.*’ Holland proposes that since the environment is actually a ‘*meta-capability*’ that enables and sustains all of humanity’s capabilities and needs, from basic sustenance, to shelter, and to aesthetic pleasures, humanity has an obligation to protect and maintain the ecological systems through judicial frameworks, since ecosystems provide the conditions for justice. Supporting the arguments of Holland (2008), Caney (2010) relies on a human rights approach to argue that nature’s protection is key to the continued provision of a range of basic human needs, and Steve Vanderheiden (2012) has further articulated such an approach as a set of environmental rights.

Discussing principles that should guide how society distributes environmental benefits and burdens, Holland (2008) proposes some form of liberal theories of justice, similar to Martha Nussbaum’s (2007) ‘*capabilities approach,*’ which however does not adequately address the issue under discussion. Holland argues that the capabilities approach should be extended to account for the environment’s instrumental value to human capabilities. Given this instrumental value, protecting capabilities requires establishing certain environmental conditions as an independent ‘*meta-capability.*’ When combined with Nussbaum’s nonprocedural method of political justification, this extension provides the basis for adjudicating environmental justice claims. The author applies this extended capabilities approach to assess the distribution of benefits and burdens associated with climate change.

Such an approach is invaluable, and as discussed by Martha Nussbaum (2007), it becomes essentially an improvement, as long as the usual invisibility of the natural world in conceptions of justice remains ignored. The proper functioning of human societies that depend on the environment and ecosystems to ensure sustainability for both human’s and nature’s wellbeing is anchored on justice, and that remains central and primary in the concepts and versions of environmental justice, proposes Nussbaum. That approach extends the considerations of justice even further into nonhuman recipients and from environmental to ecological justice, in spite of numerous criticisms of extending the capabilities approach to the nonhuman realm.

Moving from discussions into action, in September 2008, Ecuador became the first country in the world to recognize such rights for nature in its constitution, ensuring ecosystems should have ‘*the right to exist, persist, evolve, and regenerate,*’ at the same time empowering any person or organization to defend, protect, and enforce those rights through the Rights of Mother Nature or ‘*Pacha Mama.*’ Ecuador’s decisive move was followed along the same set of principles by Bolivia in 2010. In April 2010, Bolivia hosted the Peoples Conference on Climate Change and the Rights of Mother Earth, at which time the Universal Declaration of the Rights of Mother Earth, modelled on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, was

drafted, approved by the Conference, and forwarded to the United Nations for consideration by the UN General Assembly. The Universal Declaration of the Rights of Nature was presented during a session of the General Assembly on April 20, 2011. That was a bold movement in history to change the established human-centred mindset and recognise the rights of ecosystems and start procedures for inserting Ecojustice within judicial frameworks around the world, and universally. Some 20 other countries have followed since.

In 2021 Chile officially recognized the rights of nature in its constitution, and in 2022, Panama's President signed the Rights of Nature into national law, establishing a list of Earth-centric principles to be upheld, including '*in dubio pro natura*,' which means that when in doubt, one must act in favor of protecting Nature, and respecting planetary boundaries for the whole country, not just for human society, or industry, or '*the one percent*.'

These more recent legal approaches reject the old tradition of regarding nature as property to be used for human benefit, into one that acknowledges and recognizes that nature and natural systems generally are rather rights-bearing partners with which humanity has co-evolved. Such laws may now heralding a new beginning, one of an evolution toward recognition of the inherent rights of nature to exist, thrive, and evolve.

Apart from the decisions of Bolivia, Ecuador, Chile, Panama, and others to boldly declare that nature should be at par with humans in terms of rights, New Zealand and India went further by conferring personhood to rivers. The debate on ecosystem/nature's rights have been going on for a number of years with many arguing that nature have intrinsic rights too, and others that humans are the only species that can claim for rights. Nevertheless, all through the debates it appears those who believe in the rights of nature/ecosystems have more substance to back their call, as opposed to the few who still believe in the supremacy of humans over all other living entities. The centre point of such discussions, agreeing or disagreeing, appear to rest on whether humanity should continue being solely anthropocentric, and continue to poison and destroy the planet, or change course and move towards an ecocentric/biocentric mindset to regulate activities and save whatever of nature is left.

However, the situation in other countries around the world, especially in the developed industrial nations of the North, remains indifferent, and the debate about ecological rights and ecojustice goes on. The discussions of Burdon (2010) explain that practice of environmental law seeks to protect the environment by '*regulating*' human interaction, but only in exceptional circumstances are communities provided the legal right to say no to an activity or stop any existing project that is liable to have deleterious effects on the functions of ecosystems. Unless a human or representative body can demonstrate direct harm as a result of the activity, they cannot meet the requirement of standing to challenge the action. Moreover, earlier Rolston (1993) explained that since the concept of rights that has worked so well to protect humans and human dignity represent cultural progress, there was no reason for the same rights model proving troublesome when used to protect the biological world.

Discussing the needs to establish rights on behalf of greater environmental/ecological protection, Vanderheiden (2012) recognizes three main areas for developing environmental/ecological rights, including:

1. Extensionist theories that link existing rights (for example to subsistence or territory) to threats of harm from exacerbated resource scarcity, pollution or rapid environmental change;

2. Rights to specified environmental goods or services, such as rights to a safe environment and the capacity to assimilate greenhouse gas emissions; and
3. Rights that protect the interests of parties not currently recognized as having rights, including nonhuman subjects, natural objects and future generations.

The author attempts at capturing the potential for and primary challenges to the development of rights as instruments for safeguarding the planet's life-support capacities, and discusses features, proposals, and analyses that argue the need to create an avenue of recourse against ecological degradation, whether on behalf of human or nonhuman right holders. This instrumental environmental approach to justice considerations is quite clear, and it pushes theorists to consider the crucial reality of human immersion in environments that can either provide basic needs or endanger them.

Looking more towards the practical and economic aspects of ecojustice, and discussing '*The Rule of Ecological Law*,' Carver (2013) notes that human enterprise has already transgressed global ecological limits. Carver recommends that the legal regime should support a radical re-focusing of the economy on reduction of its throughput of material and energy, remembering the statement of the 2010 Global Biodiversity Outlook 3:

The target agreed by the world's Governments in 2002, to achieve by 2010 a significant reduction of the current rate of biodiversity loss at the global, regional and national level as a contribution to poverty alleviation and to the benefit of all life on Earth, has not been met. There are multiple indications of continuing decline in biodiversity.

The statement of the 2010 Global Biodiversity Outlook 3 is rather a stark warning that neglecting protection of natural systems for the benefit of lifeforms on earth may contribute to hardships for the human species. Reid and Nsoh (2014) adopt a middle of the way approach by stating that '*there are existing tools, increasingly being used, for the conservation of biodiversity,*' in other words, the conservation of natural systems, or ecosystems, and these include conservation covenants, biodiversity offsets and payment for ecosystem services. We are simply being reminded that these are the same human attempts that have failed in producing positive results to this day.

However, while steps are being taken to introduce laws based on such approaches, a second and contrary response has been to reject such developments as a '*privatization*' or '*commodification*' of nature, which should instead be seen as part of humanity's shared '*common heritage*.' Again, such attempts require consideration of the basic position of ownership of wild flora and fauna, the extent of the property rights of landowners and others with interests in the land, and of how far the state is justified in restricting, and even taking over these rights for conservation, or exploitation, purposes, conclude Reid and Nsoh (2014).

Similarly, Lucy and Mitchell (1996) suggested in an earlier discussion that the nature of private rights should be limited to secure the interests of biodiversity, and proposed reformulating the concept of property on the basis of stewardship rather than absolute ownership. Cullinan (2011) suggests that any complete reassessment of the position of landowners would result in a far-reaching challenge to the conventional way of thinking about the human relationship with nature posed by the new emerging concepts of '*Wild Law*' or '*Earth Jurisprudence*,' which Reid (2013) points out would call for laws that would allow,

Freedom for all members of the Earth Community to play a role in the continuing co-evolution of the planet.

However, the stark reality remains that under the current system of law in almost every country, nature is still considered to be property, a treatment that confers upon the owner the right to destroy nature and ecosystems on that property. The concept of the '*rights of nature*,' recognizes that ecosystems and natural communities are not merely property that can be owned and disposed of, but entities with independent rights to exist and flourish. Laws recognizing the rights of nature would thus change the status of natural communities and ecosystems to being recognized as rights-bearing entities with rights that can be enforced by law.

Before there could be any discussion of ecojustice, whether nature has any rights that need to be acceptable or accepted, has to be established. This is probably the stage at which the proposal of Stone (1972), that is endowing nature with personhood and ensuring legal rights for natural objects should be given serious consideration. Since the natural environment cannot speak for itself, Stone proposes guardians to speak for and defend it, as has been enacted in the Rights of Mother Earth and the Universal Declaration of the Rights of Nature framed by Ecuador (2008) and Bolivia in 2010.

Representation, as proposed by Stone (2010), has been a popular theme in environmental ethics and political theory, and the importance of representation should also arise from the fact that nonhuman entities cannot speak for themselves. This is not a reason to exclude '*the inarticulates*' from the sphere of concern, because different strategies can be employed to enable their representation. Related suggestions involve representative proxies for nonhuman animals (Feinberg 1980), trustees, or dedicated environmental institutions that '*speak on behalf of nature*' (Eckersley 1999; 2004; Baxter 2005; Dobson 2010), '*reflexive democracy*' (Schlosberg 2007), and learning to '*listen to nature*' through appreciating the signals it sends (Dobson 2014).

Based on Stone's philosophy, Kramer (2010) proposes the interest theory to protect nature's rights and its vital interests, even in the absence of cognitive awareness and sentience. Kramer further argues that nature can thus have rights according to the interest theory since it has interests that need protection. However, Cupp (2009) believes the concept of right is essentially human, for '*it is rooted in the human moral world and has force and applicability only within that world.*' In their reflections about rights, Traulsen and Nowak (2006), Callicott (2013) and Farine et al., (2015) are of the opinion that in accepting that intrinsic values are associated with nonhuman individuals and natural systems, and even if the concept of ecocentrism at times appears at odds with post-enlightenment Western ethics, ecocentrism should be supported by current multi-level understanding of physical and biological sciences, and should expand rather than oppose Western ethics, as proposed earlier by (Nash, 1989).

Traulsen and Nowak (2006) contends that no individual of any species can exist in isolation from '*conspecifics*' or other species, and it needs to be recognized that multi-level genetic selection remains the key concept in evolution of both humans and other species, animate or inanimate. Rolston III (1985) and Washington et al. (2017) have elaborated on why the eco-evolutionary dynamics of the biosphere demands a re-assessment of the established philosophical worldview that individual members of a single species, *Homo sapiens*, are the sole agents of moral worth. The authors are concerned that:

Justice for nature has been ignored or denied, being something of a taboo that academia avoids. Further denial will only exacerbate the ongoing biodiversity crisis.

Scholars have been looking at strategies, perceptions, and concepts that may justify rights for ecosystems and convince the opposition that there is indeed a case for protecting nature through the concept and practicality of rights and ecojustice. Under what he calls the '*legal operational*' aspect of extending rights to nature, Stone (2010) proposes three factors that must exist for nature to count jurally:

1. Standing,
2. Recognition of injury, and
3. Ability to act as beneficiaries.

Stone (2010), affirms that as long as the belief that nature/ecosystems should have rights is not recognized, '*we cannot see it as anything but a thing for the use of us,*' by those holding rights, that is humans. To support his arguments, Stone (2010) points out that the rights of nature have been recognised in municipal ordinances in some countries, the Constitution of several countries, in the '*Pacha Mama*' of Bolivia and Ecuador, and in a proposed United Nations Declaration; so the question of doubts as to its legitimacy does not and should not arise. Additionally, to further re-enforce Stone's arguments, both Chile and Panama have now followed the philosophy adopted in the '*Pacha Mama*' or the rights of nature through the '*Rights of Mother Earth.*'

Transgression of the ecological limits as stipulated by the Stockholm Resilience Centre and discussed by Rockström et al. (2009), and an urgency to resort to the concept of degrowth to justify sustainable development and ensure ecological sustainability have also been proposed as avenues for ecological rights and justice. In his study, '*The Rule of Ecological Law,*' Carver (2013) bases his plea for ecological justice on the fact that since humanity has already transgressed ecological limits, '*the legal regime should support a radical re-focusing of the economy on reduction of its throughput of material and energy.*' In other words, Degrowth should be a further consideration in ecological legal instruments. Sustainable degrowth would necessarily involve a downscaling of production and consumption that would in turn increase human well-being and enhance ecological conditions and equity on the planet, claims Carver.

Degrowth has been a subject of discussions since the mid 70s (Gorz, 1977; Georgescu-Roegen, 1979), followed by the 1972 Club of Rome Report, '*The limits to growth,*' and taken further by the movement '*Degrowth for Ecological Sustainability and Social Equity,*' with a declaration of their Paris 2008 Conference to the effect that:

We therefore call for a paradigm shift from the general and unlimited pursuit of economic growth to a concept of '*right-sizing*' the global and national economies.

In addition, the statement of their Barcelona 2010 Conference declares:

An international elite and a '*global middle class*' are causing havoc to the environment through conspicuous consumption and the excessive appropriation of human and natural resources. Their consumption patterns lead to further environmental and social damage when imitated by the rest of society in a vicious circle of status-seeking through the accumulation of material possessions. While irresponsible financial institutions, multi-national corporations and governments are rightly at the forefront of public criticism, this crisis has deeper structural causes.

These '*deeper structural causes*' can only be associated with the wanton destruction of the integrity of natural systems or ecosystems, systems that are being denied rights. Earlier supporters of the degrowth concept, Daly (1996), Daly and Farley (2004) and Heinzerling and Ackerman (2007) are in agreement that the rule of ecological law, operating as a legal complement to ecological or degrowth economics, would provide a basis for establishing

ecological legal regimes. Carver (2013) recognizes that the sustainable degrowth movement would provide context for the emergence of the rule of ecological law. The debate on the economic and ecological issues associated with degrowth continues, and further information can be found in the contributions of Martinez-Alier et al. (2010), Kallis, (2011) and Buch-Hansen (2018).

Over the years discussions have been numerous and varied regarding the best formula to ascertain ecosystems/nature's rights, not in treaties, directives, or other forms of soft laws as is the present practice, but within judicial systems both nationally and internally. The late British Barrister Polly Higgins, together with her co-workers has undoubtedly been the most active in defending the rights of nature, and reconciling Social Justice with Ecojustice. Promoting the '*Rights of Nature*' and the concepts of '*Wild Law*,' and campaigning for an '*Ecocide Law*' has been Higgins lifelong project. Higgins (2010) declares that the world needs a '*Planetary Declaration on the Rights of Nature*,' which should lead to the development of a viable ecocentric democracy, or '*Ecodemocracy*', as discussed by Eckersley (2004); Baxter (2005) and Schlosberg (2007). Eco-democracy has been defined by Gray and Curry (2016) as:

Groups and communities using decision-making systems that respect the principles of human democracy while explicitly extending valuation to include the intrinsic value of non-human nature, with the ultimate goal of evaluating human wants equally to those of other species and the living systems that make up the Ecosphere

Higgins et al. (2013) further argue that nature has an existential right to exist, in compatibility with the spirit of Earth Jurisprudence, defined by Cullinan (2014) as:

A philosophy of law and human governance that is based on the idea that humans are only one part of a wider community of beings, and that the welfare of each member of that community is dependent on the welfare of the Earth as a whole.

Although arguments about '*human nature*' and '*nonhuman nature*' keep recurring, and even when both are '*of nature*', humanity is considered as a specific, but not always better case as it has '*culture*'. The discussions and arguments of Gare (1995), Rolston III (2001) and Plumwood (2001) contends that humans and their culture are a '*distinctive*' part of nature, with the ability to recognise '*difference*' without however seeking to create dualisms. However, Kohn (2016) believes that by removing the distinction between culture and nature, '*we may be ignoring that human interests often do not coincide with those of nonhuman nature*,' claiming that:

In deconstructing the dichotomy between humans and non-humans, we might be simultaneously erasing the issue of human chauvinism and speciesism.

Kohn, 2016 argues that offering expansion of the social justice category to include nonhuman nature would be '*similar to arguing that nature is part of culture, rather than the other way around*.' The result, observes Kohn, would be turning nature into an adjunct pushed into social justice around the edges of social justice's primary meaning, which is '*justice between and for humans*.' Additionally, Vucetich et al. (2018) are of the opinion that to '*see nature as being part of culture is both anthropocentric and denies the evolutionary reality that humans and their culture are part of nature*.' Vucetich et al. (2018) conclude their arguments stating that:

Ignoring any concept of '*ecological justice*' for nonhuman nature, and seeking to push this into social justice, is a mistake both ethically and strategically in terms of a holistic conservation strategy for life on Earth.

Misrecognition by ignorance is too often resorted to, and common in the human treatment of nature, claims Kopnina (2016), when referring to ways in which nature is often dismissed as a potential ‘*subjected one.*’ At least certain kinds of ecological systems can be argued to have integrity that can be harmed, and have been discussed by Schlosberg (2007), Crescenzo (2013), and Westra et al. (2016). Additionally, Martin et al (2016) recognizes three major reasons for incorporating the concept of recognition into approaches to environmental and ecological justice, summarized as:

1. Recognition provides a useful concept for addressing the claims of justice that concern the respect of community values, practices, and even the survival of cultures and communities (Schlosberg 2007; Kortetmäki 2016b).
2. The concept of recognition allows analysing reasons beyond distributive environmental and ecological injustice.
3. The correction of various forms of ignorance or lack of respect is a prerequisite for achieving justice in the distributional and political realm as well (Kortetmäki, 2016b).

Moving away from the discussions and arguments of environmental scholars, it would also be necessary to consider what strategies international organizations have resorted to, and what prescriptions have been suggested to curtail environmental destruction through the recognition of nature’s rights to justice. What then does ecological justice entail from the lens of international platforms? The main international policy interventions undertaken to address issues of natural resource conservation, pollution, preservation of habitats and species, biodiversity, the ozone hole, the greenhouse effect, indigenous and subsistence ways of livelihood (local interests and rights) and poverty include:

- The 1972 United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm;
- The 1980 World Conservation Strategy publication of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN);
- The 1987 report from the World Commission on Environment and Development;
- the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in Rio, also known as the ‘*Earth Summit*’;
- The 1995 Copenhagen World Summit for Social Development;
- The 2000 Earth Charter;
- The 2002 Johannesburg Summit (WSSD-2002);
- The Paris Agreement. UN-UNFCCC COP 21 (2015).

However, from 1972 and up to 2015 international prescriptions do not appear to have taken a lead in matters pertaining directly to environmental/ecological justice, and neither have they been able to grasp the importance of connecting environmental harm and destruction with the protection of and justice for ecosystem. All that the world has seen so far is a backlog of recommendations, policy instrument, treaties, international agreements, and a congestion of soft laws, policy frameworks and instruments, more in terms of assumptive recommendations than practical realities.

The Earth Charter, finalized in 2000, was proposed for United Nations endorsement at the World Summit on Sustainable Development (WSSD) in Johannesburg, South Africa in 2002. The Charter strongly advances an ecocentric worldview, urging in Principle 1a that we:

Recognize that all beings are interdependent and every form of life has value regardless of its worth to human beings.

The document stresses on compassion for humanity and nature as a whole, and urges justice for both. Discussing the philosophy and the spirit of the Charter, Soskolne (2008) and Washington (2015) declare that:

It is probably the best international document we have to help demystify sustainability

However, although it was analyzed and mentioned positively in some speeches at the WSSD (2002), the final Johannesburg Declaration of 2002 did not endorse the Earth Charter, and nor recommend it for further consultations.

To foster the type of transnational and international leadership needed to accomplish the objectives of international policy instruments with regards to ecosystems protection, Carmen Gonzalez (2012) offers and proposes the following recommendations for consideration:

1. Policy and legal frameworks should focus more on the causal factor (humans) and not mainly on the resultant effects;
2. Education and its institutions, agencies, and leaders should, through every available apparatus and resource, realign back to the goal of enlightenment based on democratic values of equality and common good, for future ethical and authentic leadership;
3. All innovations and developments should be scholarly, practical, and environmentally certified; and
4. An innovative way of understanding ecologies across varying geographical space, cultures, races, and walks of life should be fostered and made a priority.

What also keeps recurring in international environmental policies is the proposition that environmental destruction can be resolved through sustainable development and poverty reduction. While those two elements may have some implications in protecting ecosystems, the bigger picture of treating the cause at the source appears to escape attention. In an earlier analysis of policy and legal international frameworks associated with environmental protection and justice, Wissenburg (2006) claims that political theories rather than laws of nature rule political decisions. For ecologists to extend the circle of compassion (ecojustice) to include not only humans but also sentient animals and even to accept the intrinsic value of nature itself needs to create a form of association with the concept of ecological sustainability, and Wissenburg proposes that:

Ecological sustainability is the demand that the ecology, meaning the system of interconnected and interdependent species and natural phenomena on the planet, be perpetuated.

What in fact Wissenburg (2006) proposes is concentrating on ecocentric prescriptions. However, while the concepts of ecocentrism and biocentrism have been advocated as a catalysts for systems change and a change in attitudes towards accepting nature, natural systems and ecosystems as being entities with rights to justice, ecocentrism has been labelled '*anti-human*' or as contrary to concerns for social justice, as purported by Smith, (2014). It should be clarified however that proponents of ecocentrism and ecojustice are not anti-human, insists Curry (2011). On the other hand, Vucetich et al. (2018) among others argue that the perception that '*conservation should trump social justice*' should be looked upon as being misanthropic. However and as previously discussed by Rowe (1994), Curry (2011) claims that given that ecological integrity is an indispensable prerequisite for human existence and flourishing, true ecocentrism cannot be misanthropic or anti-human, even if, in some situations, ecojustice may need to be dominant and overriding.

How and why proponents of ecocentrism and ecojustice are not anti-human, and that claims by Vucetich et al. (2018) are mistaken should be clarified. As such, Curry (2011) supports the earlier arguments of Rowe (1994), declaring that '*ecocentrism is not an argument that all organisms have equivalent value.*' The discussions and arguments of Washington et al., (2018) better clarify ecocentrism and anthropocentrism and their influences on environmental legislations, and specifically on the connotation of nature's rights and ecojustice.

Sympathisers and supporters of Anthropocentrism appear to be numerous, since a number of scholars (Hayward, 1997, Norton, 2004; 2009, Hassoun, 2011, Wilson, 2018, Batavia, 2020), mostly in the field of ethics, claim there have always been a misunderstanding as to the meaning of '*Anthropocentrism,*' especially when it is compared to ecocentrism or biocentrism. Kopnina et al. (2018) describe Anthropocentrism briefly as:

In its original connotation in environmental ethics, it is the belief that value is human-centred and that all other beings are means to human ends.

While definitions of ecocentrism and anthropocentrism may not be enough to understand their implications, from discussions so far it appears the debate about anthropocentrism, ecocentrism and biocentrism will go on through the years to come, but the immediate problem right now is about the unregulated destruction of the environment and ecosystems, how best to enact appropriate laws and regulations to curtail the scourge, and most of all how to resort to the concept of justice to ensure that environmental/ecological justice becomes a reality. To that effect, the analysis of Crist (2012) supported by the views of Strang (2016) conclude that:

In its '*human supremacy*' approach, anthropocentrism has been constantly privileging human welfare over that of all other living beings, thus denying attempts at establishing instruments for ecological justice, or the '*Rights of Nature.*'

Crist (2012) assigns the main problem in discussions about eco or environmental justice to the anthropocentric mindset that persists around the world, and more so in the associated common belief of '*human supremacy*' over nature. As such, anthropocentric policies of privileging human welfare over that of all other living beings deny ecological justice, as has been previously discussed and established by Eckersley (1999), Schlosberg (2004), and Baxter (2005).

Although most definitions are based on environmental ethics, concerned environmental scholars have argued that anthropocentrism is both ethically and ecologically wrong and is at the root of ecological and environmental crises generally. However, Crist (2012) claims that some environmental ethicists still argue that critics of anthropocentrism are misguided or even misanthropic. They contend that:

1. Criticism of anthropocentrism can be counterproductive and misleading by failing to distinguish between legitimate and illegitimate human interests.
2. That humans differ greatly in their environmental impacts, and consequently, addressing human inequalities should be a precondition for environmental protection.
3. Since ecosystems constitute the '*life-support system*' for humans, anthropocentrism can and should be a powerful motivation for environmental protection.
4. Human self-love is not only natural but helpful as a starting point for loving others, including nonhumans.

It should be noted that such contention from the defenders of anthropocentrism has been expressed as early as 2004 by Norton, arguing that:

If reasonably interpreted and translated into appropriate policies, a non-anthropocentric ethic will advocate the same environmental policies as a suitably broad and long-sighted anthropocentrism.

And again Norton re-iterates his beliefs in 2009, reaffirming that:

If adding the idea of intrinsic value to that of enlightened human interest creates no difference in mandated behaviors, and indicates no real changes in behavior from following '*broad anthropocentrism*,' then the '*metaphysical*' idea that nature has '*intrinsic value*' is shown to have at best only ideological and rhetorical use.

The concept of '*broad anthropocentrism*' may also have been at the core of the thesis of Nicole Hassoun (2011) '*The anthropocentric advantage? Environmental ethics and climate change policy*,' to even blatantly contend that:

Even though climate change is likely to cause problems for many parts of nature, it will probably be good for some other parts.

The proponents of the benefits of anthropocentrism obviously attempt at making a case to perpetuate human-centred politics and policies, but appear to miss out the association with nature's rights. Associating ethical challenges to a discussion about why justice for humans should embrace ecocentrism and also encompass ecological justice (Schlosberg 2004), or justice between species (Baxter 2005), it is realized that the concepts of ethics, or more specifically environmental/ecological ethics are more often ignored, environmental justice concentrating on the human domination of the environment or nonhuman species as a focus of moral concern.

In their discussion: '*Rehabilitation of Anthropocentrism: A Critical Approach*,' De and Nanda (2015), although adopting a more conciliatory approach, explains the main objectives of Anthropocentrism in their conclusions and final statement:

So according to the anthropocentric attitude there is no ethical offence by enjoying a superior position on earth to dominate the nature to use its resource to fulfill the interest of human beings as only human beings have the right to be treated as ethical entity having inherent value which must be respected.

Most of the arguments of proponents of the anthropocentric way humans live and work appear to go against the grain of arguments to the contrary. In his discussion about anthropomorphism: '*The Arrogance of Humanism*' Ehrenfeld (1981) delivers a rather damning statement:

Anthropocentrism as a parochial, narrow-minded, submoral approach to the earth that is largely responsible for the environmental predicament.....A kind of species egoism and species selfishness: The nonhuman world is one giant resource for us.

However, discussions and debate about anthropocentrism and ecocentrism should not be one that pitches one group against another, but rather one that examines the future of humanity, which is invariably tied with natural systems, since '*man is also of nature*.' Moving from a purely anthropocentric approach to an ecocentric orientation requires that all social practices incorporate ecological sensitivities and heightened awareness of the intrinsic value of non-human entities. For those interested in eco-justice and green criminology, it is vitally important to describe what an eco-just future might look like, and this includes recognition of and support for already existing ecocentric initiatives evident in some policies and practices

across criminal justice institutions in several parts of the world. To re-enforce the case for ecojustice, the concept of '*Green Criminology*' has also been discussed and argued as reasonable grounds for protecting ecosystems through judicial instruments.

Since both ecological harm and justice have been highly misunderstood and contested concepts, White (2013) finds that the main reason is because much of the actual harm is perceived to be legitimate and lawful, and that contention is mainly achieved through embedding harmful practices into everyday human activities. As such there is a need to take environmental harm seriously, and the notion and concept of '*Green Criminology*' is premised on that need, conceptualising harm beyond the conventional understandings of crime, as discussed by Beirne and South (2007) and South and Brisman (2013).

Green criminologists generally agree that destructive and damaging human activities that harm environments need greater attention than has been the case within the domain of criminology. Although there is already numerable laws and conventions that deal with environmental crimes and harms, yet White (2013) finds little attention has been paid to environmental/ecological crimes or green crimes specifically, or to analyse how these are actually working, or how best to apply criminological insights from areas such as crime prevention to matters regarding ecological crime.

Within the field of green criminology, White, (2011) recognizes a more expansive definition of environmental/ecological crime or harm that should include:

1. Transgressions that are harmful to humans, environments and nonhuman animals, regardless of legality *per se*; and
2. Environmental-related harms that are facilitated by the state, as well as corporations and other powerful actors, insofar as these institutions have the capacity to shape official definitions of environmental crime in ways that allow or condone environmentally harmful practices.

With regard to green criminology, White, (2008) contends that:

An eco-justice perspective should refer to the broad orientation of green criminology directed at exposing different instances of substantive social and environmental injustice.

From an eco-justice perspective, White recommends that environmental harm would be best framed in terms of justice, which in turn is based upon notions of '*human, ecological, and animal rights, and broad egalitarian principles.*' As an all encompassing proposition, White recommends three broad approaches to justice, each with their own specific conceptions of what is harmful:

1. Human rights and environmental justice: in which environmental rights are seen as an extension of human or social rights so as to enhance the quality of human life, now and into the future.
2. Ecological citizenship and ecological justice: in which it is acknowledged that humans are merely one component of complex ecosystems that should be preserved for their own sake via the notion of the rights of the environment.
3. Animal rights and species justice, in which environmental harm is constructed in relation to the place of nonhuman animals within environments and their intrinsic right to not suffer abuse, whether this be one-on-one harm, institutionalised harm or harm arising from human actions that affect climates and environments on a global scale.

Picking up from the discussions of White (2008; 2011; 2013), the analysis of Nurse (2017) concentrates on '*Green Criminology*' as another of the unresolved issues in international environmental law and justice, and elaborates on how there is a necessity for justice systems to do more than just consider anthropocentric notions of criminal justice, and rather consider applying the notion of a broader '*green*' perspective to environmental harms, ecological justice, and the study of environmental law and criminality; the author finds that environmental law justice should include crimes affecting the environment and non-human nature. Nurse further claims that since the concept of ecological justice and species justice are within the perspectives of green criminology, there should also be considerations on how justice systems can provide protection and redress for an environment that also harbours other species, apart from humans.

Nurse (2017) claims that such an approach to ecojustice and commonly expressed views on '*Green Criminology*' need to be of importance in discussions about Eco/Environmental justice since:

This unique study of social harm offers a systematic and critical discussion of the nature of environmental harm from an eco-justice perspective, challenging conventional criminological definitions of environmental harm.

Both White and Nurse appear to be in agreement with Higgins' perception of ecological crime: the crime of Ecocide.

Rather than only attempting to infuse Nature's Rights into legal protection, and Ecojustice into human and social rights, other considerations should also be visited. Constanza (2010) brings into the debate the association of ecological protection and justice into the concept of ecological economics, explaining that it is a trans-disciplinary field bridging across not only ecology and economics but also psychology, anthropology, archaeology, and history, and defines the goals of ecological economics as:

Its goal is to develop a deeper scientific understanding of the complex linkages between humans and the rest of nature, and to use that understanding to develop policies that will lead to a world which is ecologically sustainable, has a fair distribution of resources (both between groups and generations of humans and between humans and other species), and efficiently allocate scarce resources including '*natural*' and '*social*' capital.

In analyzing and discussing the concept proposed by Constanza (2010), Capra and Luisi (2014) propose that in order to '*develop an economy that strengthens nature's inherent ability to sustain life,*' the economy must adapt to ecological limits and principles. The authors call for a new science centered around ecological economics and the inclusion of '*the systems view of life,*' because it is grounded in systems thinking. Lovelock (1998) similarly argues that:

Ecological economics recognizes that economy, nature, and culture are integrated parts within a '*living*' organism.

In a nutshell, the central concept of ecological economics is sustainability, and this could be approached both qualitatively and empirically, claims Capra and Luisi. The difficulty arises in achieving a profound understanding of nature and ecosystems, which should include systems and systems thinking, Deep ecology, Ecosystems philosophy, Ecological archaeology, Ecological ethics/Bioethics, Ecological philosophy, Ecological morality, Ecological economics, Ecosystem services, Ecological/planetary boundaries, and Ecological psychology.

Still within efforts to search for better strategies to protect nature/ecosystems, a new perception of ecojustice, '*Eco-Democracy*,' has been defined and discussed by Gray and Curry (2016) as:

Groups and communities using decision-making systems that respect the principles of human democracy while explicitly extending valuation to include the intrinsic value of non-human nature, with the ultimate goal of evaluating human wants equally to those of other species and the living systems that make up the Ecosphere

The concept of Environmental/Ecological Democracy (ED), yet another of the unresolved issues in international environmental law and justice, is associated with the concept of the Rights of Nature, summarized by Venkatasamy (2022). Environmental Democracy or Green Democracy, discussed by Ungaro (2005), Mitchell (2006), Gray and Curry (2016) and Petters (2017) revolves around how to make a commitment to environmental protection compatible with democratic processes as commonly practiced in other domains. It is slowly evolving as a liberal notion that presupposes a link between democracy and ecology, sometimes proposed in such terms as '*sustainable development*' or '*green capitalism*' or '*green consumerism*.' However, it is packaged, the objective being to induce a switch from human-centred policies that are far from being fair play to the environment, to one that considers nature or ecological systems as part of policy planning in terms of democratic processes.

And Peters (2017) has the last word on justifying the concept:

Since the last quarter of the twentieth century, we have witnessed world-wide schizophrenia in our '*development*' policies.-----To understand this schizophrenia and to evolve policy frameworks to respond to this crisis from the ecological perspective is the need of the hour.

Another avenue that has also been explored to ensure ecojustice is the recognition of ecosystems as a right bearing entity. Discussed by Borrás (2016), the case for legal recognition of ecosystems is getting stronger, and (Burdon, 2011) argues that one of the avenues would be through the philosophy of Earth Jurisprudence; rather than argue that humanity and the anthropocentric human culture are part of nature, it should be accepted that nature is part of culture. However, Morton (2007) contends that '*then nature just becomes window-dressing*,' an add-on to culture, removing any agency from nature, and simply giving nature '*some passing moral consideration*,' or even be granted some rare '*intrinsic value*.' However, Curry (2011) finds that nevertheless such an approach subscribes fully to the '*Greater Value*' assumption that nature has some intrinsic value, but laments that:

But wherever humans and nature conflict, humans take precedence and whenever there is the question of justice, the process has been engulfed into social justice.

Additionally, in deliberating on the '*Rights of Nature*' and the demand for ecological/environmental justice, both Strang (2016) and Borràs (2016) elaborate on a case for legal recognition of nature and ecosystems based on the arguments of Cullinan (2011) and Burdon (2011). Both are in support of applying the concepts of *Earth Jurisprudence* to protect natural systems. Supporting the philosophy of Earth Jurisprudence, the authors contend that:

If nature is ruled out as deserving any moral consideration, then justice for nature is similarly abandoned, as nature doesn't count, has no '*rights*' and is not deemed to be a locus of intrinsic value.

Does Theology have a say in environmental/ecological justice? A proposition to that effect emanates from Dr Norman C. Habel, eminent Professor of Biblical Studies in the USA. In his discursive proposition ‘*Guiding Ecojustice Principles*,’ Habel (2016) sets his theme as:

To recognize our kinship with all members of the Earth community and to assume a posture of empathy and partnership with the Earth, rather than assume dominion over Earth.....that the language of human dominion over the Earth is not acceptable but is, in fact, one of the factors that has led to the ecological crisis.

Habel has developed a set of principles in consultation with ecologists, including the concepts of Thomas Berry (1998), and claims the principles he formulated have been further refined in consultations with and during workshops concerning both ecology in general and the relationship between ecology and theology.

These principles, a reflection of what several scholars have discussed, can be summarized as:

1. The Principle of Intrinsic Worth, asserting that the Earth, and its components have value of themselves, not because they have utilitarian value for humans and nor is this intrinsic value to be confined to sentient or living beings.
2. The Principle of Inter-Connectedness. The Earth is a community of inter-connected living things which are mutually dependent on each other for life and survival, and not a controlled or mechanical structure consisting of independent parts governed by the so-called laws of nature, each species and each member of each species are connected by complex webs of interrelationships.
3. The Principle of Purpose. The Earth and all its components are part of a dynamic cosmic design within which each piece has a place in the overall goal of that design.
4. The Principle of Mutual Custodianship, where responsible custodians can function as partners with, rather than rulers over the Earth to sustain its balance and diversity.
5. Principle of Resistance. The Earth and its components not only suffer from injustices at the hands of humans, but actively resist them in the struggle for justice.

Professor Habel’s theological discussion and principles reinforce the propositions and recommendations that environmental, legal, and social scholars have been actively analyzing, discussing, and proposing over the past decades. In addition, no doubt Professor Habel has been inspired by the message and statement of Pope Francis (Laudato Si-2015), and calling for:

Today we have to realize that a true ecological approach always becomes a social approach; it must integrate questions of justice in debates on the environment, so as to hear both the cry of the earth and the cry of the poor.

Moving from theology into the political aspects of ecological protection through justice, in her thesis about ‘*Justice in and to Nature*,’ Kortetmäki (2017) claims that too much of political theorising has led to assumptions as to the reasons why nonhumans are excluded from direct concern. The author supports her arguments by referring to the observations of Dobson (2014) in that the difficulty in distinguishing between politically meaningful communication and political ‘*noise*’ has meant that ‘*other signals than human speech are nothing but noise*.’ Kortetmäki re-iterates what has been repeated over and over,

That for a long time nature has been regarded merely as a resource, as a resource that should be managed sustainably.

Kortetmäki obviously refers to the anthropocentric view and belief that nature as a resource ‘*should be managed sustainably*’ for human exploitation and use. However, the recognition of nonhumans rejects the ‘*political superiority of man*’ over nature and brings the nonhuman

world to the realms of politics and justice. Under such a new situation, argues Kortetmäki, a denial of the integrity and agency of ecological systems entails wrongdoing to nature and is not just a matter of unsustainability or injustice to future generations, as proposed by the sustainability concept.

Although the idea of the capabilities of ecological collectives still remains contested, claims Kortetmäki (2017), the case that capabilities can be collective is made broadly in the community capabilities literature (Stewart, 2005; Ibrahim 2006; Schlosberg and Carruthers, 2010; Murphy, 2014). In support of Kortetmäki's arguments, Greenberg (1994) and Keynes (2011) describe political economy/political ecology as concerns about the relationship existing between power distribution and access to resources, while cultural ecology concerns itself with human-environmental relationships. The authors summarise their conclusions as:

The construct of ecological (in)justice lends itself to a theoretical framework of political ecology which is a combination of political economy and cultural ecology.

Kortetmäki (2017) also finds that the concept of ecological justice will require modifying the capabilities notion of nature, expanding the application of justice to non-sentient beings as well as systemic entities like ecosystems in the same way as recognition of human capabilities lead to self-respect and dignity. Elaborating on the advantages of the capabilities-based view of ecological justice, the author claims that it can at least be used as an approach to *'minimal rather than full justice.'*

Taking the earlier discussions of Sen (2001), Nussbaum (2007) and Holland (2008) even further, Kortetmäki (2017) recognizes that the idea of threshold capabilities may well result in a less demanding set of duties in comparison to distributional approaches to ecological justice, discussed by Schlosberg (2001), Baxter (2005) and Sievers-Glotzbach (2013), and as such Kortetmäki (2017) proposes in conclusion that there should be three major reasons for incorporating the concept of such recognition into approaches to environmental and ecological justice:

1. Recognition provides a useful concept for addressing the claims of justice that concern the respect of community values, practices, and even the survival of cultures and communities (discussed by Schlosberg 2007, Kortetmäki, 2016b).
2. The concept of recognition allows analysing reasons beyond distributive environmental and ecological injustice: the correction of various forms of ignorance or lack of respect is a prerequisite for achieving justice in the distributional and political realm as well (discussed by Kortetmäki 2016b).
3. Analysing recognition helps reveal particularities that are *'masked'* as universalities in contemporary societies. They are hidden and unquestioned assumptions that produce and maintain inequalities, exclusions, and that impede hearing nonhuman voices within the political sphere full of human noise (discussed by Dobson 2014).

Discussing the environmental capabilities framework, both Kortetmäki (2018) and Melin (2021) contend that for nonhuman to flourish, there should be a certain requirement for capabilities whose realisation comprises a set of functions that are essential to the flourishing characteristic of a given creature. A central idea of the environmental capabilities approach is that the community of justice includes all entities whose integrity and capabilities can be harmed by human activities. This has engendered debate on the capabilities of ecological systems. Can they, in the first place, have capabilities? And if they can, what kinds of capabilities should be considered as central capabilities of ecological systems?

In spite of numerous discussions regarding the many angles from which the concept and practicalities of ecojustice should become a reality of environmental law and justice, there still exists the contention that too much of academia has been slow even to mention the idea of ecojustice, focusing purely on social justice, and environmental justice (justice for humans). Even those who acknowledge the intrinsic value of nature often fail to acknowledge the need to speak out for ecojustice or to mention the concept. Instead, they seem to be attempting to ‘*push justice for nature into the periphery of social justice,*’ claim Washington et al. (2018).

In several discussions, Washington (2013), Oliver et al. (2015), Cafaro et al. (2017); Washington et al. (2017; 2018a;b) and Piccolo et al. (2018) the authors similarly argue that justice for nature has been affected by concerns about dualisms and by strong anthropocentric bias. These authors claim that recent propositions to push justice for nature into social justice, effectively weakens any move to establish ecojustice within institutional, legal or global mindsets. If nature is ruled out as deserving any moral consideration, then justice for nature is similarly abandoned, as nature does not count, has no ‘*rights*’ and is not deemed to be a of any ‘*intrinsic*’ value, observe the authors. Obviously, Washington and contemporaries appear to have concentrated on the large group of scholars defending anthropocentrism and justice for humans rather than for nature and ecosystems.

At the same time, Washington et al. (2018) find that justice for nature, or ecological justice (ecojustice) or ecological injustice as discussed by Akinola, and Lowery (2018) still remains a confused term to this day. In recent decades, justice has predominantly been limited to humanity, with a strong focus on social justice, and its spin-off, environmental justice applied to people, leading to a situation where scholars have concentrated on ecological ethics and an ecocentric approach to ecojustice, claims Washington.

However, Washington appears to have a preference for distributive justice, discussed earlier by Schlosberg, (2001) Baxter (2005) and Sievers-Glotzbach (2013). Examining the formal rationale for ecocentrism and ecological ethics, Washington et al. (2018) recommends that distributive justice should be resorted to in an effort to reconciling social justice and ecojustice to ensure effective conservation, proposing that:

As this underpins attitudes towards justice for nature, or ecojustice, and show how justice for nature has been affected by concerns about dualisms and by strong anthropocentric bias, distributive justice can also apply to nature, including an ethic of bio-proportionality.

The conclusions of Washington et al. (2018) elaborates, as several scholars have, on the wrong direction taken by the social aspects of the environment, rather than considering nature as an environment in its own right, and the value of ecosystems to humanity, stating that:

Humanity is faced with a serious predicament it does not wish to acknowledge – the accelerating ecocide and the mass extinction of life on Earth – due entirely to human actions. Such denial has been aided by a dominant anthropocentric worldview that denies nonhuman nature any value, agency or justice.

Similar and in support to the discussions of Washington et al. (2018), in analysing the environmental moral philosophy of justice, Wienhues (2020) finds that too many terms have been used for ecological justice, and while some scholars concentrate on interspecies justice, most agree that non-human living beings do not deserve justice for reasons they have elaborated, which are mostly based on principles of sustainability. However, the author contends that sustainability should not be regarded as a responsibility owed to each other as

fellow humans, but also as what humans owe other creatures with which they share one planet, proposing that:

Biodiversity conservation is not only a matter of securing the wellbeing of future human generations, but also a matter of doing justice to non-human living beings.

And Wienhues (2020) further stress upon her arguments in declaring that:

Even more importantly, I consider distributive justice to be the most important building block in a theory of ecological justice because of the materiality of environmental relations and problems.

Concerns have also been expressed about the present environmental crisis and the pace at which environmental destruction is moving. The discussions of Mace et al. (2018) and Boyd (2017) explain how scientific evidence indicates that the global environmental crisis is accelerating and that environmental laws have so far not been able to reverse the trend, and that at the most, existing laws regulate rather than stop the destruction of the natural world. Another central issue will be how conflicts between rights of nature and corporate or human rights and interests will be adjudicated. This weighing will determine whether rights of nature will be effective, propose the authors.

Earlier, Burdon (2010) stated that conflicts between nature and human activities happen on a massive and systematic scale, especially when people and corporations have rights and nature does not, with the result that nature frequently loses out, as evidenced by the continuing deterioration of the environment. Stone (2010) also argues that while laws shifted to recognise racial and gender equality, it did not appear laws were ready to consider seriously an extension of rights to ecosystems. Anticipating such resistance, Stone (2010) further notes that:

Throughout legal history, each successive extension of rights to some new entity has been, thereto, a bit unthinkable ... each time there is a movement to confer rights onto some new 'entity', the proposal is bound to sound odd or frightening or laughable. Whether such reactions are because of fear in having to share rights, or fear of having to respect other living entities need to be ascertained.

Although Burdon (2020) maintains that nature cannot possibly recognise the rights of others, in discussing the broader concept of nature's rights and protection in a changing world Khandelwal (2020), adds a new dimension to the debate, and more in support of Stone's perceptions of nature (1972), states that:

With environment protection laws throughout the world displaying their own set of limitations, in the light of climate change, the concept of Environmental Personhood becomes all the more crucial and enterprising.

Analyzing such reactions of fear discussed by Stone (2010), Piccolo et al. (2018) and Washington et al. (2018) argue that such fears may result from the consequences that recognising the rights of nature would place in terms of limits on human property rights, and such fears have already triggered reactions from those opposing endowing nature with rights. More than a decade earlier, Jensen (2004) remarked that '*extending rights to nature would be simply patronising, rather patriarchal and imperialistic.*' Jensen believes that to '*extend or bestow or recognise rights in nature would be, in effect, to domesticate all of nature; to subsume it into the human political apparatus.*' Almost two decades earlier, Plumwood (2002) raised a final objection to extending rights to nature and ecojustice, arguing that '*legal rights are excessively individualistic.*'

And even earlier Raz (1986) argued that there could be a right if and only when some interest, such as an aspect of well being or one of moral interest ‘*of some entity capable of being a right holder is sufficient to ground a duty to care for and promote the interest in a significant way,*’ while Feinberg (1980) considered that an entity could possess rights if the possibility of either harm or benefit could be demonstrated and the entity was conscious of such treatment, concluding that:

Without awareness, expectation of belief, desire, aim and purpose, a being can have no interest; without interests, he cannot be benefited; without the capacity to be benefited, he can have no rights.

What have been academic discussions and arguments, from the statement of Feinberg (1980) through four decades to the arguments of Picolo et al. (2018) and Washington et al. (2018) have not brought the world any nearer to recognising nature’s Rights and reconnect humanity to ecosystems through legal instruments. As Wahington et al. (2018) rightly puts it:

Justice for nature remains a confused term. In recent decades justice has predominantly been limited to humanity, with a strong focus on social justice, and its spin-off - environmental justice for people.

Rather than considering nature as a separate entity for which rights are being claimed as a purely academic exercise, examining today’s situation, the complexity of human activities interfering with the proper functioning of ecosystems have become apparent. Gordon (2017) has been amongst those most fervent in arguing a case for the theory of personhood, as proposed by Stone (1972; 2010). To put minds at ease Gordon states that need not ‘*be seen only as a foil for corporate power*’ even if a corporation as a non-human entity now enjoys the status of personhood. Basing his arguments on jurisdictions that have developed versions of legal regimes granting rights directly to nature in and for itself, Gordon (2017) states:

The ways in which the acknowledgement of the rights of nature has played out in the jurisdictions in which it is present also evidence this statement. Law and its social context are of course mutually constitutive; it is possible today to imagine that new views on environmental precariousness and new legal conceptions of the standing of nature might combine to make the doctrine of environmental personhood a robustly protective one..

Taking a different direction, May and Daly (2018a; b), discuss and introduce the concept of Global Environmental Constitutionalism, a recent phenomenon within the field of constitutional law, international law, human rights, and environmental law. It explores the constitutional incorporation, implementation, and jurisprudence of ecological rights, duties, procedures, policies, and other provisions to promote environmental protection. Knox (2019) recognises that environmental constitutionalism in some regions already accepts the recognition of nature as a bearer of judicially cognizable rights, leading to a shift in thinking about the world, and the relationship of human beings to the world.

Can ecojustice be also part of environmental management? Discussing the ecosystem approach to ecojustice, De Lucia (2019) elaborates on how it has been broadly understood as a legal and governance strategy for integrated environmental and biodiversity management, has been adopted within a wide variety of international environmental legal regimes, and as such provides both a narrative, a policy approach and in some cases legally binding obligations for States to implement what has been called a ‘*new paradigm*’ of environmental management. The discussion of Schlosberg (2019a) on the other hand concentrates on the application of justice, and questions whether the present model of justice specifically for humans should not transcend our understanding of life as applicable to other living entities..

After decades of discussions, agreements, disagreements, and hesitations of almost criminal proportions, ecosystems and ecosystems health and wellbeing remain at the mercy of only one species of the whole construct of the planet's biodiversity: *homo sapiens*. Bold initiatives to reverse the situation have been few, and no doubt that more recently both Chile and Panama are showing the rest of the world the right direction.

The Constitution of Chile (2021) now declares:

The current legal system fails to represent the intrinsic value of nature, with laws and decision-makers typically only considering economic or human interests.

The constitution further defines nature as '*an active and passive subject of law*', and calls for:

A law that shall define and penalise the crime of Ecocide.....any unlawful or wanton act perpetrated knowing or ought to know that there is a substantial likelihood that it will cause serious, extensive or lasting damage to the environment.

The Constitution of Panama (2022) now defines nature as

A unique, indivisible and self-regulating community of living beings, elements and ecosystems interrelated to each other that sustains, contains and reproduces all beings.

In Feb. 2022, Panama's President signed the Rights of Nature into national law, establishes a list of Earth-centric principles to be upheld, including '*in dubio pro natura*,' which means that when in doubt, one must act in favour of protecting nature. The principles also stress on respecting planetary boundaries for the benefit of all, not just human society, or industry, or '*the one percent*'.

The legislation comprises of six paragraphs of rights extended to nature, including:

1. The right to exist, persist and regenerate its life cycles,
2. The right to conserve its biodiversity, and
3. The right to be restored after being affected directly or indirectly by any human activity.

In contrast with widely held anthropocentric frameworks which place humans centrally, such new laws see the beginning of an evolution toward recognition of the inherent rights of Nature '*to exist, thrive, and evolve*.' This evolving legal approach acknowledges that the traditional environmental regulatory systems generally regarding nature as property to be used for human benefit, rather than a rights-bearing partner with which humanity has co-evolved.

Such bold initiatives, even if too few, are indicative that finally acceptance of nature as a right bearer is finding its place in the human mindset, and ecojustice will soon be the obvious alternative to systems and prescriptions that have not worked. The law of Ecocide, Higgins (2010) lifelong dream and project, is gaining ground, and in 2021 Siddique (2021) reports that the draft law officially defines ecocide as:

Unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts.

To this day some 16 countries have adopted Ecocide laws in their domestic legal systems, others being on the way. However, both Ecojustice and Ecocide have not been accepted as an internationally punishable crime by the United Nations.....yet, and Ecojustice still remains at the periphery of international environmental law and justice.

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